

Site: SPHINX Season NS 80
Area: E SPHINX Square NI/E9- Locus Number (4)
TEMPLE 10

Progress of Excavation Until SAT 5/VI/80 clearing continued across
square in loose fairly clean sand - somewhat mottled, w/ mod inclusions
like cement - max of this to W side of Sq SAT 5/VI/80 ZAM
ordered 2 probes - small trenches; one in roughly SW corner 1.60 x 1.70 m.
at top, another in roughly NE corner, 1.80 x 2.00 m. // 6/VI/80 when
I arrived in morning probe in SW corner (PROBE 1) had gone down to
Bedrock - levelled through continuation of dry loose sand w/ stone chips and
mod. inclusions (about 75 cm thick in probe) (2)(?); then through ~
46 cm packed damp sand-mud mix w/ mod inclusions (like a plastic →

Locus Description _____

Location in Square _____

Under Locus _____ Over Locus _____

Locus Dimensions _____

Levels _____

Analysis of non-artifactual materials _____

